

SUCCESSION FACTORS AND EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN KENYA

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ABSTRACT

The study was on succession factors and employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. The study was premised on four specific objectivities namely human resources planning, organizational leadership, organizational culture and organizational policy. To strengthen the conceptual framework the study adopted theories such as human capital theory, transformational leadership theory and theory of organizational culture. This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design aimed at collecting large number of qualitative and quantitative data at a point in time so as to examine the influence of succession factors on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. The study findings established that all the four variables have a significant effect on employee performance of public universities in Kenya. The study recommends that special focus should be given to organizational factors when executing duties as they are imperative in employee performances. Sharing of organization vision, encouraging employees to increase their conceptualization, comprehension, and analytical capability should be fronted in all aspects to enhance employee performances. Training should be carried out periodically because it provides skills, knowledge and motivation to the employees which in turns improves their performances. Organizational culture should be formulated in a manner that can encourage respect of authority, fostering an innovative culture, culture of high employee involvement, adaptable culture that drives human resource morale and retention, market turnover and productivity.

Keywords: Human Resource Planning, Organizational Leadership, Organizational Culture, Organizational Policy, Employee Productivity.

1.1 BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

The concern for succession among organisations whether public or private has been a lingering issue among human resource practitioners and authorities for years. Effective leaders and human resource managers in different fields through the centuries have developed and implemented succession plans for their organisations which paved way for the survival of the concerned firms. The need for succession planning practices is necessitated by the concern for the future. Succession creates avenues for needs, talents and this includes activities designed to attract, extend and keep the best pool of staff at all levels in the interest of the organisation. With succession, employees have expectations of staying with employers for years in the hope that after a few years of distinguished service, they might graduate to the next ranks of management aided by mentoring and helping to enhance organisational commitment (Mensa, 2021).

Therefore, the need for factors that predict employee productivity has become more critical. One of the factors that could lead to healthy organizational climate, increased morale, motivation and productivity is human resource planning factor, leadership factor, organizational culture and organizational policy factor and moderated by the size of the state corporation (Badeyo, 2020). Employees' commitment may go a long way in determining how well organizations achieve their set goals and objectives. As a result, it will be pertinent for organizations to pay attention to the wellbeing and of their employees in order to increase their productivity (Stephen & Stephen, 2021). Hence, it follows that a responsible organization will strive to provide enabling work environment and make sure that the organizational framework gives shape and support to its succession that will enhance employees' productivity.

Human Resource Planning was initially designed to improve the process for recruiting and developing people with the required skills and aptitude to meet current employee needs. The various aspects of Human Resource Planning are recruitment, selection, on-boarding, mentoring, performance management, career development, leadership development, replacement planning, career planning, recognition and reward (Egerova, 2020). Competition and the lack of availability of highly talented and skilled employees make finding and retaining talented employees 'major priorities for organizations (Fegley, 2020). In order to attract and retain the best talent anywhere in the world, an organization must have a strong and positive employer brand (Goudreau, 2012).

Employee productivity (sometimes referred to as workforce productivity) is an assessment of the efficiency of a worker or group of workers. Productivity may be evaluated in terms of the output of an employee in a specific period of time. According to Mathis and John (2019) productivity is a measure of the quantity and quality of work done, considering the cost of the resources used. The more productive an organization, the better its competitive advantage, because the costs to produce its goods and services are lower. Better productivity does not necessarily mean more is produced; perhaps fewer people (or less money or time) was used to produce the same amount. McNamara (2020) further states that, results are usually the final and specific outputs desired from the employee. Results are often expressed as products or services for an internal or external customer, but not always. They may be in terms of financial accomplishments, impact on a community; and so, whose results are expressed in terms of cost, quality, quantity or time.

Measuring productivity involves determining the length of time that an average worker needs to generate a given level of production. One can also observe the amount of time that a group of employees spends on certain activities such as production, travel, or idle time spent waiting for materials or replacing broken equipment. The method can determine whether the employees are spending too much time away from production on other aspects of the job that can be controlled by the business. Employee productivity may be hard to measure, but it has a direct bearing on a company's profits. An employer fills his staff with productivity in mind and can get a handle on a worker's capabilities during the initial job interview. However, there are several factors on the job that help maximize what an employee does on the job (Lake, 2020).

In South African the concept of succession planning has long been the subject of study in the private sector, but not in the public sector. Nevertheless, it is increasingly discussed in the public sector, and dangers of not having a succession planning mechanism in place are becoming

apparent. Singh (2019) points out that succession planning is a subject of concern for managers worldwide as organizations face problems in filling critical positions where they need employees with a specific set of skills along with experience. According to Ahmadi, Shamsuddin, Chan, and Wahad (2020) succession planning is “a strategic process that reduces leadership or management gaps and gives opportunities for top talent to develop skills necessary for future roles”. The absence of succession planning can hold back an organization as the demand for both the quantity and quality of talented employees will grow worldwide (Farashah, Nasehifar, & Karahrudi, 2019).

In Kenya for instance, employees’ productivity is a major concern today since it translates to high turnover. Globally, employee retention is enhanced by management of the most talented employees especially the ones working on foreign duties (Anyango, 2020). There is growing need for companies to come up with strategies aimed at ensuring that employees are retained for the good of organizational success (Chelimo, 2019). The sustainability of any organization is determined by retention of its key employees (Hanaysha, 2019). Furthermore, the aspect of employee retention is a human resource management issue which ensures that employees stay in employment for a long time (Lake, 2020).

1.1.1 Employee Productivity

According to Mathis & John (2003), productivity is a measure of the quantity and quality of work done, considering the cost of the resources used. The more productive an organization is, the better its competitive advantage. This is because of the efficiency of the resources that have been used. McNamara (2005) further affirms that, results are usually the final and specific outputs desired from the employee. They may be in terms of financial accomplishments, impact on a community; and so whose results are expressed in terms of cost, quality, quantity or time. McNamara (ibid) also asserted that measuring productivity involves determining the length of time that an average worker needs to generate a given level of production. It could also be the amount of time that a group of employees spends on certain activities such as production, travel, or idle time spent waiting for materials or replacing broken equipment. The method can determine whether the employees are spending too much time away from production on other aspects of the job that can be controlled by the business.

Employee productivity may be hard to measure, but it has a direct effect on a company's profits. An employer fills his staff with productivity in mind and can get a handle on a worker's capabilities during the initial job interview. Yet, there are several factors on the job that help maximize what an employee does on the job (Lake, 2007). Brady (2008) express that, perhaps none of the resources used for productivity in organizations are so closely scrutinized as the human resources. Many of the activities undertaken in an HR System are designed to influence individual or organizational productivity. Pay, appraisal systems, training, selection, job design and compensation are HR activities that are directly concerned with productivity. Furthermore, Bernardin (2007) maintains that controlling labour costs and increasing productivity through the establishment of clearer linkages between pay and performance are deemed to be crucial component of human resource management (HRM) so as to achieve competitive advantage. In addition, increased concerns over productivity and meeting customer requirements have prompted renewed interest in methods designed to motivate employees to be more focused on meeting (or exceeding) customer requirements and increasing productivity.

2.0 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Succession Planning is a very important management strategy that enables organizations to achieve organizational goals and objectives effectively and efficiently. The current scenario in most Kenyan organizations is that this component has been ignored. This is evidenced by at times managers being politically appointed and, in most cases, they have been picked from fields that are not related to organizations where they are meant to manage. In other cases, tribal considerations are used not qualifications (Nekesa, 2018).

According to Koketso (2020), many public sector organizations have substantial uncertainties about leadership capabilities. Additionally, poor career planning and low levels of integration between the personal and professional aspirations of employees continue to persist for a variety of reasons, including succession planning. Kock and Burke (2018) concur that most public service organizations lack succession planning. Therefore, the present study aimed to determine the factors related to succession.

Several studies have been done on succession planning and employee productivity such as Amahwa and Egezza (2021), Chelimo (2019), Farashah, *et al.*, (2019) and Kwame (2020) many of whom have studied about how succession planning affects employee performance and employee productivity. Various scholars have examined the concept of human resource planning and related impact on employee productivity. For instance, Sukayri (2019) examined how succession planning and employee productivity and noted that the most county governments did not have coherent succession planning processes due to over-reliance on foreign technocrats who are moved around other agencies at the expiry of their contract. Huselid, (2019) conducted a study to determine whether county governments had human resource planning strategies and how they impacted Employee Productivity.

Amahwa and Egezza (2021) reviewed literature on succession planning and employee productivity in Kenya whereas Nekesa (2018) examined the influence of succession planning and employee productivity at Nzoia sugar company. Badeyo (2020) evaluated the influence of succession planning and employee productivity in listed telecommunication firms. The aforementioned studies examined succession planning and employee productivity and limited themselves to succession planning and employee productivity whereas this study examines succession factors and employee productivity in state corporations in Kenya. Further this study examines objectives such as human resource planning factor, organizational leadership factor, organizational culture factor and organizational policy factor affects employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

3.0 RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

This study was based on general and specific objectives as follows:

3.1 General Objective

To examine succession factors and employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

3.2 Specific Objectives

1. To evaluate the influence of human resources planning factor on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

2. To investigate the influence of organizational leadership factor on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.
3. To determine the influence of organizational culture factor on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.
4. To examine the influence of organizational policy factor on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

4.0 RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

This study's research hypothesis will be based on null hypothesis as follows:

H₀1: Human resources planning factor have no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

H₀2: Organizational leadership factor have no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

H₀3: Organizational culture factor has no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

H₀4: Organizational policy factor has no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

5.0 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The study reviewed the following theories to strengthen the conceptual framework:

5.1 Human Capital Theory

Hills (2009) assert that human capital is the time, experience, knowledge and abilities of an individual household or a generation, which can be used in the production process. This theory contends that peoples learning capacities are comparable to other natural resources, when effectively exploited the results are profitable to the organization. Therefore, the human capital theory helped to examine how Human Resource Planning could enhance recruitment. processes that are essential to Employee Productivity. The relevance of this theory to Human Resource Planning is that human capital consisting of various components, skills, time, experience and knowledge which is talent embedded in individual persons.

5.2 Transformational Leadership Theory

Burns (1978) first conceptualized this theory when he introduced the concept of leadership that is transformational among political leaders. Burns stated that transforming leadership is a process in which a leader and his/her followers work towards the advancement to a higher level of morale and motivation. Bass (1985) then extended Burns' work on transformational leadership theory. Bass explained the psychological mechanisms that underlie transforming and transactional leadership. Bass added to the initial concepts of Burns (1978) to help explain how transformational leadership could be measured, as well as how it impacts follower motivation and performance.

By considering Bass (1985) conceptualization of the theory of transformational leadership, one key point stands out that distinguishes leaders is that others champion change through continuous improvement, while some would rather play within the precincts of what is known. Bass further reiterated that most leaders with greater followership are most often transformational by practice or nature. Northouse (2014) notes that a more expanded and refined version of transformational

leadership that was based on the work of Burns (1978) now exists. Bass argued that transformational leaders motivate followers to transcend their own self-interest for the sake of the team; and moving followers to address high-level needs. In other words, the leader transforms and motivates followers through idealized influence, intellectual stimulation and individual stimulation, and individual consideration.

5.3 Theory of Organizational Culture

Handy (1993) framework argues that culture can be classified based on degree of centralization and formalization. Centralization considers the extent to which power and authority is concentrated at the top of the organization. Centralization considers the extent to which power and authority is concentrated at the top of the organization. Formalization contents to the extent to which rules, policies and procedures direct organizational activities. The framework contends that there are four types of cultures in organizations. In Power or Club culture, Handy uses a spider’s web as an analogy to depict the culture. Organizations that use this culture have divisions based on functions or products. However, relationship and connection to the spider in the middle matters most than formal titles and positions. Power and influence are concentrated at the center and loses importance the further you go from the center. This culture is mostly if found in small entrepreneurial organizations. It is excellent for speed of decision, where is speed is more important, Centralization considers the extent to which power and authority is concentrated at the top of the organization.

6.0 CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework

7.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

7.1 Research Design

This study adopted a cross-sectional survey research design aimed at collecting large number of qualitative and quantitative data at a point in time so as to examine the influence of succession factors on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. A cross-sectional survey research design enabled collection of data about a given phenomenon within a limited time horizon which can help describe incidences of events or provide an explanation of factors related to an organization (Saunders, Lewis, and Thornhill, 2019).

7.2 Target Population

The study targeted 30 public universities in Kenya. The study will target university council members, university vice chancellors and heads of departments. Therefore, the study targets 320 being council members, vice chancellors and heads of departments in public universities in Kenya.

7.3 Sample Size

The total sample size for this study was obtained using the formulae developed by Saunder *et al.*, (2018) together with Miller and Brewer (2019) and the adjusted sample size was 178 as per workings below. With a study population of 320 being council members, vice chancellors and heads of departments in public universities in Kenya. With a confidence interval of 95 percent, the sample size will also be determined using the formula given by Miller and Brewer (2019) as shown.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N (\alpha)^2}$$

Where: n= the sample size,
N= the sample frame (population)
The sample size was 178.

7.4 Data Analysis and Presentation

Qualitative as well as quantitative methods of data analysis was used to analyze the research variables. A Likert scale was adopted to provide a measure for qualitative data. The scale helped to minimize the subjectivity and make it possible to use quantitative analysis. The numbers in the scale were ordered such that they indicated the presence or absence of the characteristic to be measured Kothari and Gang, (2018). This mix of tools is necessary because whereas some aspects of the study where qualitative others was of quantitative nature.

8.0 RESULTS

8.1 Descriptive Statistics

The section presents the descriptive statistics on human resource planning, organizational leadership, organizational culture, organizational policy and employee productivity.

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Mean	Std. Deviation
Human Resource Planning	4.01	0.61
Organizational Leadership	3.97	0.52
Organizational Culture	4.25	0.64
Organizational Policy	3.90	0.51
Employee Productivity	3.98	0.49

The average mean score for human resources planning was 4.01 with a standard deviation of 0.61, the mean score for organizational leadership was 3.97 with a standard deviation of 0.52, mean score for organizational culture was 4.25 with a standard deviation of 0.64, the mean score of organizational policy was 3.90 with a standard deviation of 0.51 and employee product.

This implies that human resource planning and organizational culture contribute significantly to employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. The variables namely organizational leadership and organizational policy minimally affect employee productivity.

8.2 Correlation Analysis

Pearson Bivariate correlation coefficient was used to compute the correlation between the dependent variable (employee productivity) and the independent variables (human resources planning, organizational leadership, organizational culture and organizational policy). According to Sekaran, (2015), this relationship is assumed to be linear and the correlation coefficient ranges from -1.0 (perfect negative correlation) to +1.0 (perfect positive relationship). The correlation coefficient was calculated to determine the strength of the relationship between dependent and independent variables (Creswell, 2020).

In trying to show the relationship between the study variables and their findings, the study used the Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation. This is as shown in Table 2 below. According to the findings, it was clear that there was a positive correlation between the independent variables human resources planning, organizational leadership, organizational culture and organizational policy, and the dependent variable employee productivity. The analysis indicates the coefficient of correlation, r equal to 0.718, 0.244, 0.681 and 0.478 for human resources planning, organizational leadership, organizational culture and organizational policy, respectively. This indicates positive relationship between the independent variable namely human resources planning, organizational leadership, organizational culture and organizational policy and the dependent variable employee productivity with human resources planning having the highest contribution.

Table 2. Pearson Correlation Correlations

	Employee Productivity	Human Resource Planning	Organizational Leadership	Organizational Culture	Organizational Policy
Employee Productivity	1				
Human Resource Planning	.718**	1			
Organizational Leadership	.244*	.233*	1		
Organizational Culture	.681**	.726**	.471**	1	
Organizational Policy	.478**	.277**	.644**	.528**	1
	150	150	150	150	150

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

8.3 Coefficient of Determination (R^2)

To assess the research model, a confirmatory factors analysis was conducted. The four factors were then subjected to linear regression analysis in order to measure the success of the model and predict causal relationship between independent variables (human resources planning, organizational leadership, organizational culture and organizational policy) and the dependent variable (Employee Productivity).

Table 3 Coefficient of Determination (R^2) Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.796 ^a	.633	.615	2.12905

a. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Policy, Organizational Leadership, Human Resource Planning, Organizational Culture

The model explains 63.3% of the variance (R Square = 0.619) on employee productivity. Clearly, there are factors other than the four proposed in this model which can be used to predict financial sustainability. However, this is still a good model as Bryman and Bell, (2018) pointed out that as much as lower value R square 0.10-0.20 is acceptable in social science research. This means that 63.3% of the relationship is explained by the identified four factors namely human resources planning, organizational leadership, organizational culture, and organizational policy. The rest 36.7% is explained by other influence of supplier in procurement performance in tea buyers in Mombasa not studied in this research. In summary the four variables include human

resources planning, organizational leadership, organizational culture and organizational policy or determines 63.3% of the relationship while the rest 36.7% is explained or determined by other factors.

8.4 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

The study used ANOVA to establish the significance of the regression model. In testing the significance level, the statistical significance was considered significant if the p-value was less or equal to 0.05. The significance of the regression model was as per Table 4 below with P-value of 0.00 which is less than 0.05. This indicates that the regression model is statistically significant in predicting influence of procurement performance. Basing the confidence level at 95% the analysis indicates high reliability of the results obtained. The overall ANOVA results indicate that the model was significant at $F = 2.542$, $p = 0.042$.

Table 4 ANOVA
ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	176.950	4	44.237	2.542	.042 ^b
	Residual	2523.743	145	17.405		
	Total	2700.693	149			

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Productivity

b. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Policy, Organizational Leadership, Human Resource Planning, Organizational Culture

8.5 Coefficients

The researcher conducted a multiple regression analysis as shown in Table 5 to determine the relationship between succession factors and employee productivity in public universities in Kenya and the four variables investigated in this study.

Table 5 Coefficients
Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	29.978	2.479		12.091	.000
	Human Resource Planning	.363	.085	.059	4.271	.000
	Organizational Leadership	.382	.108	.075	3.537	.001
	Organizational Culture	.600	.156	.064	3.846	.003
	Organizational Policy	.476	.088	.661	5.409	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Productivity

The regression equation was:

$$Y = 29.978 + 0.363 X_1 + 0.382 X_2 + 0.600X_3 + 0.476X_4$$

Where.

Y = the dependent variable (Employee Productivity)

X₁ = Human Resources Planning

X₂ = Organizational Leadership

X₃ = Organizational Culture

X₄ = Organizational Policy

The regression equation above established that taking all succession factors into account (Employee productivity in public universities) constant at zero employee productivity in public universities in Kenya will be 29.978. The findings presented also showed that taking all other independent variables at zero, a unit increase in human resource planning would lead to a 0.363 increase in the scores of employee productivity in public universities in Kenya; a unit increase in organizational leadership would lead to a 0.382 increase in the employee productivity in public universities in Kenya; a unit increase in organizational culture would lead to a 0.600 increase the scores of employee productivity in public universities in Kenya and a unit increase in organizational policy would lead to 0.476 increase the scores of employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

Table 6 Test of Hypothesis

Hypothesis Statement	Regression Results	Decision
H₀₁: Human resources planning factor have no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.	t = 4.271 P = 0.000	Reject H ₀₁ null hypothesis human resource planning has a significant influence on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.
H₀₂: Organizational Leadership have no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.	t = 3.537 P = 0.001	Reject H ₀₂ null hypothesis organizational leadership has a significant influence on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.
H₀₃: Organizational Culture has no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.	t = 3.846 P = 0.003	Reject H ₀₃ the null hypothesis organizational culture man has a significant influence on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.
H₀₄: Organizational Policy has no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.	t = 5.409 P = 0.000	Reject H ₀₄ .null hypothesis organizational policy has a significant influence on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

9.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

9.1 Conclusion

Human Resources Planning

Since there was a strong positive correlation between the independent variable human resource planning and the dependent variable employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. From the study findings on coefficients, t- values of 4.271 and p-values of 0.000, this result rejected the null hypothesis that human resources planning has no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. Therefore, the study concludes that human resources planning has a significant influence on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

Organizational Leadership

Since there was a strong positive correlation between the independent variable organizational leadership and the dependent variable employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. From the study findings on coefficients, t- values of 3.537 and p-values of 0.001, this result rejected the null hypothesis that organizational leadership has no significant influence on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. Therefore, the study concludes that organizational Leadership has a significant influence on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

Organizational Culture

Since there was a strong positive correlation between the independent variable organizational culture and the dependent variable employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. From the study findings on coefficients, t- values of 3.846 and p-values of 0.003, this result rejected the null hypothesis that organizational culture has no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. Therefore, the study concludes that organizational culture has a significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

Organizational Policy

Since there was a strong positive correlation between the independent variable organizational policy and the dependent variable employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. From the study findings on coefficients, t- values of 5.409 and p-values of 0.000, this result rejected the null hypothesis that organizational policy has no significant effect on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. Therefore, the study concludes that organizational policy has a significant influence on employee productivity in public universities in Kenya.

9.2 Recommendations

That human resource planning should be strengthened to support employee productivity in public universities in Kenya. Special focus should be given to organizational factors when executing duties as they are imperative in employee performances. Sharing of organization vision, encouraging employees to increase their conceptualization, comprehension, and analytical capability should be fronted in all aspects to enhance employee performances. Training should be carried out periodically because it provides skills, knowledge and motivation to the employees which in turns improves their performances. Organizational culture should be formulated in a manner that can encourage respect of authority, fostering an innovative culture, culture of high

employee involvement, adaptable culture that drives human resource morale and retention, market turnover and productivity.

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